

Design and Development of automatic sensor based juice vending machine

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ABSTRACT

The design and development of an automatic infrared higher sensor-based vending machine is the main goal of this project. Fruit storage units for keeping fresh fruit chilled in the form of coin-operated machines are currently available on the market along with automatic fruit juice vending machines. However, our goal is to develop a powder-form vending machine that provides consumers with a quick and easy option to buy freshly squeezed juice. The juice dispensing procedure is automated by the vending machine with the use of many sensors, actuators, and a microcontroller. This project aims to Utilizing RFID tag systems for seamless transactions, customers can purchase fresh juice at any time of the day. Moreover, the mobility of these vending machines allows them to adapt to new locations effortlessly, ensuring continuous service delivery. Customers can choose their preferred juice option and finish their transaction with ease thanks to the user-friendly interface. With careful design, execution, and testing, the vending machine

Keywords: Juice vending machin, RF-IDs, Micro controller, Juice powder, Infrared higher sensor.

1. Introduction

The automatic sensor-based juice vending machine is a modern solution to the need for easy and clean drink dispensing. By using advanced sensors like those that sense proximity or flow, it makes getting juice a breeze. Customers can pick their flavor and get just the right amount they want, all thanks to the smart sensor system. Plus, safety features keep everything running smoothly. With its easy-to-use interface and options to personalize, it's not just convenient but also caters to different tastes. And it's not just about convenience – it saves time and money while keeping things clean. As more people want drinks on the go, this machine is set to change how we get our refreshments, showing us what the future of automated service looks like.

This project introduces a new kind of juice vending machine that uses sensors to work automatically. Instead of the usual complicated vending machines, this one will be easy to use, like a touch screen on your phone. You just pick your juice, and the machine does the rest – it provides fresh juice from real fruits powder right then and there, without needing anyone to help. This means you get your juice super-fast, which is perfect for people who are always in a hurry. Plus, because there's no one touching the juice, it's cleaner and safer to drink. It's designed to be convenient and good for you, so it's perfect for places like offices, schools, and anywhere else people want quick and healthy drinks. It's all about making life easier and healthier for everyone.

The automatic sensor-based juice vending machine was inspired by the need for quick and clean drink options in busy places. People are always looking for ways to make life simpler, like getting a drink while on the move. Regular vending machines are handy, but they don't always give the exact drink someone wants. Plus, lately, everyone's more concerned about cleanliness, especially after recent health issues. So, the idea was to create a vending machine that not only makes getting juice easier but also keeps things super clean. the plan is to make a vending machine that's easy to use and safe. The big goal is to change how drinks are served in public places, making it faster, more convenient, and way cleaner for everyone. The background for this project arises from the evolving demands of consumers and advancements in technology. As modern life continues at a rapid pace, people increasingly seek efficient and hassle-free solutions for their daily routines, including quick access to beverages in public areas like malls, airports, and workplaces. While traditional vending machines have provided some convenience, they often lack customization options and fail to meet

rising standards of hygiene and cleanliness, particularly in light of recent global health concerns. This project is motivated by the need to address these shortcomings by developing an automatic sensor based juice vending machine. The goal is to enhance convenience by streamlining the beverage dispensing process and to prioritize hygiene by implementing advanced sensor technologies that minimize direct contact and ensure a safe and sanitary experience for users. By offering customizable options and intuitive interfaces, the machine aims to meet the evolving needs of consumers while setting a new standard for efficiency and cleanliness in public refreshment services. There's been a big change in how food and drinks are made and served, all because of automation. This means using machines and technology to do tasks that people used to do. Why? Well, because people want things to be faster and easier. Think about it – everyone's always busy, right? So, we want to be able to get our food and drinks quickly, but we still want them to be good quality. That's where automation comes in. Whether it's those self-service machines at fast-food places or those big machines in drink factories that make juice, automation is making everything faster and more efficient. Plus, there's a big focus on keeping things clean and safe, especially now with all the concerns about germs and sickness. Automation helps with that too, by reducing the need for people to touch food and drinks, which lowers the risk of spreading germs. And with technology getting better all the time, like those sensors and smart devices you hear about, automation is becoming even more advanced. These gadgets can keep track of things like temperature and how much stuff is left, so everything runs smoothly. Overall, automation is changing the food and drink industry for the better, making things faster, safer, and more convenient for everyone. And as technology keeps improving, we can expect even more cool changes in the future.

2. Literature Survey

1. Truong Giang Nguyen, Ngoc Tran Le, Ngoc Dang Khoa Tran (2022).

This paper presents the system's design for the fresh orange juice vending machine. The machine services for each customer, so the system works in job production. The system consists of the juice extractor, cup dispenser, juice filling, movement of the cups, dosing, and packaging units. A new mechanism for the separate cup is developed and fabricated. The mechanism for each part is described in detail in the paper. The programmable logic controller (PLC) is applied to control the automation system based on the input signals from sensors and internal control algorithms. The results are output signals to control the actuators and motors. The fundamental model has been fabricated and do experiments. The investigation of the time and volume of juice for each cup.

2. MJ Roshan, S Shankar, R Nithya Prakash (2021)

The objective of this work is to provide a fresh juice in an effective manner to promote the people for drinking hygienic and healthy fruit juices using a single vending machine within 90 seconds. The design has three storage units which are fully refrigerated and the fruits can be placed on the top rack. Below that, a pneumatic mechanism is available to pick and place the fruits of required quantity. A mixture and crusher is made available within the machine to ease the mixing process. Mixture will convert fresh fruits into juicy state and crusher will extract juice from the fruits, milk and water ratio will be controlled by the machine. The entire process is controlled using a raspberry pi which is programmed for every movement and functions of the vending machine.

3. Nilani Ratansi, Tharaga Sharmilan (2021).

Vending Machines are automated machines that dispense selling products such as snacks, beverages, lottery tickets, and etc. It is vital to save time and reduce human energy. These vending machines are developed in the way of Non IoT based and IoT based methods. These Non IoT based machines are not smart and are not operated in real-time data, which are functioned when giving cash or card and inputs (vending things) of the machine. It is controlled by a microcontroller and distributed the given inputs. IoT-based machines are computerized, which have cashless payment facilities, order facility before going to the vending machine to order things, and can be identified the location of machines by the customer. These IoT-based machines are assisted to suppliers to identify the availability of the stocks. Simulation software and prototype are used to validate the machines. In this review, it is found that most of the vending machines developed are capable of

operating without IoT technology, and nowadays, vending machine systems are required to implement using IoT with machine learning, and artificial technologies to satisfy the customer preferences

4.Seyed Esmaceli, Ahmad Al-AbdulRazaq, (2021).

The refreshments industry is currently at a stalemate where most consumers are oriented towards typical, rigid and low-quality juice products. Most if not all vending machines are of low quality, as most of them offer products that include high amounts of preservative substances due to the machine's inability to maintain fresh products. Moreover, most if not all of the vending machines available in today's market suffer from poorly maintained exterior frames and internal components, in addition to limited functionalities. The design of an automated juice mixing machine that provides the user with a convenient access to healthy alternatives is proposed.

5.Venna Sibanda, Lorraine Munetsi, (2020).

Imagine, paying and placing an order in a food outlet only to wait for an extra twenty to thirty minutes to get the ordered products. How tiring. This is the current situation in different food outlets and shops. What if we could save time by 75% to 83% and get an order in five minutes or less? This can be achieved by the design and development of a fully fletched high-tech vending machine. Current vending machine owners are facing challenges from hacking and vandalism. The aim of this paper is to design a high-tech vending machine that can dispense a variety of products at the same time.

3. METHODOLOGY.

Fig.1

3.1 Software Development

Software development for the juice vending machine is like teaching the machine how to do its job. We write code, which is a set of instructions, to tell the machine what to do when certain things happen. For example, we write code to make the machine recognize when a cup is placed, when a juice option is selected. This code also controls how much juice to dispense and what to do if something goes wrong. Essentially, software development is about programming the machine to perform its tasks accurately and efficiently.

3.2 PROGRAM INSTALLED

```

#include <SPI.h>
#include <MFRC522.h>
#define SS_PIN 10

#define RST_PIN 9

MFRC522 mfrc522(SS_PIN, RST_PIN); // Create MFRC522 instance.

int ocan = A1; int gcan = A2; int omix = A3; int gmix =
A4; int osol
= A5; int
gsol = 5; int
lix = 3; int
pump = 4;
int lmf = 2;

void setup()
{
  Serial.begin(115200); // Initiate a serial communication  SPI.begin();
// Initiate SPI bus
mfrc522.PCD_Init(); // Initiate MFRC522

  Serial.println("Put your card to the reader..."); Serial.println();
pinMode(ocan, OUTPUT);

pinMode(gcan, OUTPUT);

pinMode(omix, OUTPUT);

pinMode(gmix, OUTPUT);

pinMode(osol, OUTPUT);

pinMode(gsol, OUTPUT);

pinMode(lix, INPUT);

pinMode(pump, OUTPUT);

pinMode(lmf, INPUT_PULLUP);

```

```

/*while(digitalRead(lmf) == HIGH)
{
    digitalWrite(pump, HIGH);
digitalRead(lmf);
}
digitalWrite(pump,
LOW); delay(100);*/ }
void loop()
{
    // Look for new cards  if ( !
mfrc522.PICC_IsNewCardPresent())
    {
return
;
}

    // Select one of the cards  if ( !
mfrc522.PICC_ReadCardSerial())
    {
return
; }

    //Show UID on serial monitor
Serial.print("UID tag
:"); String content= "";
byte letter;
for (byte i = 0; i < mfrc522.uid.size; i++)
{
    Serial.print(mfrc522.uid.uidByte[i] < 0x10 ? " 0" : " ");    Serial.print(mfrc522.uid.uidByte[i],
HEX);    content.concat(String(mfrc522.uid.uidByte[i] < 0x10 ? " 0" : " "));
content.concat(String(mfrc522.uid.uidByte[i], HEX));
}
Serial.println();

    Serial.print("Message : ");
content.toUpperCase();

```

```
if (content.substring(1) == "FD 6F B7 16") //change here the UID of the card/cards that you  
want to give access
```

```
{
```

```
    Serial.println("Authorized access");
```

```
Serial.println();  delay(500);
```

```
    while(digitalRead(lix) == HIGH)
```

```
    {
```

```
        delay(1000);
```

```
digitalRead(lix);  }
```

```
        digitalWrite(omix, HIGH);
```

```
delay(1000);
```

```
digitalWrite(osol, HIGH);
```

```
delay(1000);
```

```
digitalWrite(ocan, HIGH);
```

```
delay(2000);
```

```
digitalWrite(ocan, LOW);
```

```
delay(2000);
```

```
digitalWrite(ocan, HIGH);
```

```
delay(2000);
```

```
digitalWrite(ocan, LOW);
```

```
delay(2000);
```

```
digitalWrite(osol, LOW);
```

```
delay(1000);
```

```
digitalWrite(omix, LOW);
```

```
delay(1000);
```

```
}
```

```
if (content.substring(1) == "1D FF CF 19") //change here the UID of the card/cards that  
you want to give access
```

```
{
```

```
Serial.println("Authorized access");
Serial.println(); delay(500);
while(digitalRead(lix) == HIGH)
{
    delay(1000);
    digitalRead(lix);
}

digitalWrite(gmix, HIGH);
delay(1000); digitalWrite(gsol,
HIGH); delay(1000);
digitalWrite(gcan, HIGH);
delay(2000);
digitalWrite(gcan, LOW);
delay(2000);
digitalWrite(gcan, HIGH);
delay(2000);
digitalWrite(gcan, LOW);
delay(2000); digitalWrite(gsol,
LOW); delay(1000);
digitalWrite(gmix, LOW);
delay(1000); /*
digitalWrite(LED_R, HIGH);
tone(BUZZER, 500);
delay(300);
noTone(BUZZER);
myServo.write(180); delay(5000);
myServo.write(0);
digitalWrite(LED_R, LOW);*/
}
```

```
else {  
    Serial.println(" Access denied");  
}  
}
```

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. The customer requires multiples of choices in juices, we have been installed in two types of flavor in one machine so that customer will be having choices in one shop.
2. It may not appear to be much, but installing smart vending machines in the office can save employees valuable minutes and get them back to work faster. Making a cup of juice it will be taking 22sec to fill in 200 ml of glass.
3. People when they are likes unhealthy juices they will be facing medical issues according to the report, 66% Loss of productivity in medical report.
4. The installation of smart vending machine it helps saving in time, and will be able to stay fuller for longer. It helps in boost their energy levels.
5. Having two flavors in one vending machine so that cost reduction will be done for their dealer.
6. Our machine serves up delicious, freshly squeezed juices in seconds. With a variety of flavors to choose from, every sip is a burst of refreshment. machine offers quality juice at an affordable price.
7. our juices are packed with vitamins and nutrients, with every sip of it.

CONCLUSION

Through this project an attempt has been made to design and develop an automatic sensor-based juice vending machine with low cost and portability which marks significant milestone in vending technology. The creation of the autonomous juice vending machine with sensor technology is a notable advance in vending technology. This development includes automated the juice dispensing process, improving accuracy and reducing the need for manual intervention by combining sensors, actuators, and micro controllers. A low-cost, portable, sensor-based multi juice vending machine has been designed and developed in an effort to lower the cost of vending machines. After prototype the testing results shows that the machines dispense 200 millilitre of juice in 22 seconds and also it will take 12 seconds to fill for a glass of 100 millilitres. The overall weight of the Juice machine is around 8 kilograms which can be easily portable from one location to another with less effort and also the cost of the entire machine is around Rs.22000/- which is well below the cost of commercial machines available in market.

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